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5 Structure–ecotoxicity relationships and risk 6 assessment of 0D–3D carbon nanomaterials 7 across aquatic trophic levels

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22 **Abstract**

23 The rapid expansion in the production and application of carbon nanomaterials (CNMs) raises
24 increasing concerns regarding their environmental fate and ecological safety. Herein, we
25 present a systematic cross-trophic assessment of fourteen well-characterized 0D–3D CNMs,
26 including fullerene soot (FS), fullerene C₆₀, amino-acid-derived carbon quantum dots (CQDs),
27 single- and multi-walled carbon nanotubes (SWCNTs, MWCNTs), graphene (G1 and G3)
28 materials, graphite (GR), and nanodiamonds (ND). Acute and chronic ecotoxicity was
29 evaluated across three aquatic trophic levels representing producers (*Lemna minor*), consumers
30 (*Daphnia magna*), and decomposers (*Aliivibrio fischeri*), following OECD and ISO guidelines.
31 Toxic responses were strongly dependent on both trophic level and physicochemical properties
32 of CNMs. *D. magna* exhibited the highest sensitivity, particularly toward long, carboxylated
33 (oxidized) MWCNTs (MWCNT-COOH) (EC₅₀(48 h) = 5.8 mg L⁻¹), where toxicity was
34 associated with digestive tract accumulation and physical interference. In contrast, *L. minor*
35 was most affected by leucine-derived CQDs (EC₅₀ = 65.2 mg L⁻¹), inducing chlorosis and
36 growth inhibition. The bacterial model showed generally lower sensitivity, with toxicity
37 modulated by dispersion behaviour and surface characteristics. Across CNMs, no single
38 parameter governed hazard; rather, toxicity emerged from the interplay of dimensionality,
39 aspect ratio, dispersibility, and surface chemistry with organism-specific exposure pathways.
40 These findings highlight the necessity of integrated, multi-trophic ecotoxicological evaluation
41 for carbon nanomaterials and identify high-aspect-ratio, environmentally dispersible nanotubes
42 as priority candidates for environmental risk assessment.

43

44 **Keywords**

45 aquatic toxicity, carbon quantum dots, carbon nanotubes, cross-trophic ecotoxicity, graphene,
46 graphite, nanodiamonds

47 **1. Introduction**

48 Carbon nanomaterials (CNMs) (**Fig. 1A**), spanning 0D carbon quantum dots (CQDs) (Rosales
49 et al., 2025), 1D carbon nanotubes (CNTs) (Hughes et al., 2024), 2D graphene (Singh et al.,
50 2025), and 3D nanodiamonds (NDs) (Shenderova et al., 2019) or graphite (Yadav et al., 2025),
51 are manufactured globally at scales ranging from a few to thousands of tonnes per year (Gusain
52 et al., 2025). CNMs have gained significant industrial interest due to their unique
53 physicochemical, mechanical, optical, thermal, and electrical properties, including high
54 surface-area-to-volume ratios and tunable surface chemistry (Xia et al., 2025). These features
55 support applications in medicine, environmental protection, and energy technologies (**Fig. 1B**).

56

57 **Fig. 1** CNMs as a subject of this study (**A**) and their applications (**B**). General trophic levels
58 (**C**) and the herein studied aquatic species (**D**); own work and adapted from www.labroots.com,
59 image credit: Inhabitat (*Vibrio fischeri*); (currently correct: *Aliivibrio fischeri*).

60 Despite their technological promise, broader industrial adoption remains limited by challenges
61 in production scalability, cost, and uncertainties regarding environment- and human-health
62 impacts (Lead et al., 2018).

63 Growing awareness of the environmental occurrence of CNMs – particularly those released
64 through anthropogenic activities – has stimulated a substantial body of contemporary research
65 (Walker et al., 2002). The ecotoxicological behaviour of CNMs is inherently complex and
66 demands a holistic, ecosystem-level perspective that integrates responses across trophic levels
67 – including animals, plants, microorganisms (producers, consumers, and decomposers) – and
68 their abiotic surroundings (**Fig. 1C**) (Walker et al., 1991). Such investigations must implement
69 a comprehensive temporal framework, spanning source, environmental transformation, and
70 eventual fate, while also considering engineered interventions aimed at neutralizing or
71 mitigating adverse impacts, as well as preventative strategies designed to limit the introduction
72 and transport of CNMs into ecological systems (Singla et al., 2020).

73 At all trophic levels, comparative evaluation of the toxicity of different CNMs is frequently
74 limited, and in many cases not feasible, due to the multitude of variables that simultaneously
75 influence their behaviour in biological and environmental systems. Fundamental differences in
76 particle morphology, surface chemistry, functionalization degree, agglomeration and dispersion
77 state, and hydrodynamic diameter critically affect bioavailability and interaction pathways
78 (Boncel et al., 2016) (Boncel et al., 2017). Additional complications arise from impurities
79 originating from synthesis routes, such as residual metal catalysts from the synthesis processes,
80 that may independently contribute to observed toxicity. On the biological side, factors such as
81 nutrient availability, exposure duration, developmental stage, and the physiological condition
82 or stress status of test organisms further confound direct comparisons (Guo et al., 2008).
83 Environmental parameters, including pH, ionic strength, dissolved organic matter, temperature,
84 and water hardness, also shape nanoparticle stability and reactivity. Variability in analytical

85 methods, dose metrics (mass-, surface area-, or particle number-based), and endpoints measured
86 introduces yet another layer of inconsistency (Devadasu et al., 2013). Collectively, these
87 physicochemical, biological, and methodological factors underscore the inherent challenges in
88 deriving straightforward, cross-material comparisons in CNM ecotoxicology (Boncel et al.,
89 2015).

90 Widely adopted as standardized bioindicators in aquatic ecotoxicology, the macrophyte *Lemna*
91 *minor* (primary producer), the cladoceran *Daphnia magna* (primary consumer and keystone
92 grazer), and the bioluminescent bacterium *Aliivibrio fischeri* (sensitive microbial bioindicator)
93 (**Fig. 1D**) constitute an ideal triad for robustly assessing the environmental fate, bioavailability,
94 and trophic transfer of 0D–3D CNMs.

95 *Lemna minor* (common duckweed) is a small, surface-floating plant found in freshwater bodies
96 such as ponds. Its structure consists of several small, round leaves called fronds. Under the
97 leaves, there is a single root immersed in the water column. The plant measures 2–5 mm and
98 reproduces asexually (vegetatively) through division, which ensures low genetic variation. Its
99 ease of cultivation, rapid growth of new plants, small size, and sensitivity to harmful substances
100 make it one of the most commonly used plants as a model organism in ecotoxicology (Vulpe et
101 al., 2025). Up to date, ecotoxicological reports provide only limited and discontinuous insights
102 into the responses to CNMs of *Lemna minor* – as the most studied representative of producers.
103 This knowledge gap significantly hinders a comprehensive evaluation of their impacts on
104 aquatic macrophytes. In one but a representative study, Gamoń et al. examined the effects of
105 multiwalled CNTs (MWCNTs) and their oxidized derivatives (f-MWCNTs) on *L. minor*. Their
106 findings indicated generally low phytotoxicity: the EC₁₀ for MWCNTs was 431 mg L⁻¹,
107 whereas no EC₁₀ could be established for f-MWCNTs within the tested concentration range.
108 These results imply that pristine MWCNTs exhibit marginally higher toxicity than their

109 functionalized counterparts, although both materials demonstrate overall low adverse effects
110 toward *L. minor* (Gamoń et al., 2023). It is important to underscore that published data on the
111 toxicity of other carbon-based nanomaterials, such as C₆₀ (and its analogues), CQDs,
112 graphenoids, and nanodiamonds – to *L. minor* remain scarce. This paucity of evidence
113 underscores the need for further systematic investigations to clarify the potential environmental
114 risks associated with the expanding industrial use of CNMs.

115 *Daphnia magna* is a freshwater planktonic crustacean widely used as a model consumer in
116 ecotoxicological studies. Its high sensitivity to aquatic pollutants, short life cycle, and ease of
117 laboratory culture make it a standard test organism for assessing toxic effects at the consumer
118 level. Owing to its transparent carapace and filter-feeding behavior, *D. magna* is particularly
119 suitable for evaluating both physiological responses and interactions with suspended
120 contaminants, including nanomaterials (Grabińska-Sota, 2015; Ahmed, 2023). The
121 experimental data for **Table 1** compiles the available ecotoxicological data for selected CNMs
122 with respect to *Daphnia magna*, revealing pronounced variability in their biological effects.
123 The findings consistently indicate that the structural characteristics and morphology of CNMs
124 strongly modulate their interactions with this model organism. A recurrent outcome across
125 studies is the pronounced bioaccumulation of CNMs within the digestive tract, which appears
126 to constitute a central mechanism of toxicity. Such accumulation can physically obstruct the
127 filtering apparatus, thereby reducing food intake and compromising overall physiological
128 condition. The resulting disturbance of homeostasis often manifests as metabolic stress – most
129 notably oxidative stress – characterized by elevated levels of reactive oxygen species (ROS).

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133 **Table 1** Toxicity of selected CNMs toward *Daphnia magna*.

Nanoparticle	Dimensions	Exposure time	EC ₅₀ [mg L ⁻¹]	Observations	Source
Fullerene C ₆₀		48 h	28.50	Accumulation in the intestines and their structural damage. Reduced superoxide dismutase activity as a response to oxidative stress.	(Lv et al., 2017)
Carbon quantum dots (CQDs)	$d > 10$ nm	48 h	160.30	N/A	(Yao et al., 2018)
Single-walled carbon nanotubes (SWCNTs)	$d = 2$ nm ^b $l = 5-15$ nm ^c	48 h	2.42	Accumulation in the intestines	(Zhu et al., 2009)
Multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs)	$d = 8-15$ nm $l = 10-50$ μm	24 h	0.27	Accumulation in the intestines and decreased swimming speed due to coating of the body by the nanomaterial.	(Trompeta et al., 2019)
MWCNT-COOH	$d = 60-100$ nm $l > 50$ μm	48 h	No effects were observed. All organisms survived.	Accumulation in the gastrointestinal tract.	(Cano et al., 2017)
Graphene (G)	2-3 layers	24 h	0.09	Reduced swimming speed due to coating of the body by the nanomaterial.	(Cano et al., 2017)
Nanodiamonds (NDs)	$d = 5$ nm	21 days	0.63 (NOEC) 1.30 (LOEC)	Adhesion to the exoskeleton surface, accumulation in the digestive tract, and blockage of nutrient absorption.	(Mendonça et al., 2011)

134 ^a N/A = not available, ^b d – diameter, ^c l – length.

135 The ROS increase frequently reported in the literature likely stems from both damage to the
 136 intestinal epithelium caused by nanoparticle deposition and the secondary effects of starvation.
 137 It should also be noted that certain CNMs, including fullerene soot (FS) and graphite, remain
 138 insufficiently characterized in this context, underscoring the need for continued research into
 139 their potential ecological impacts.

140 As a representative decomposer, *Aliivibrio fischeri* is a non-pathogenic, marine Gram-negative
 141 bacterium widely used in ecotoxicological bioassays. Its bioluminescence, resulting from

142 luciferase-mediated reactions and emitted at ~490 nm, is closely linked to cellular metabolic
 143 activity and is rapidly inhibited upon exposure to toxic substances. This response forms the
 144 basis of standardized bioluminescence inhibition tests, in which *A. fischeri* serves as a sensitive
 145 and highly reproducible indicator of acute toxicity. Owing to its rapid response, ease of use,
 146 and extensive validation, *A. fischeri* remains one of the most established bacterial models in
 147 ecotoxicology (Grabińska-Sota, 2015; Christensen and Visick, 2020). The so-far studies
 148 generally reported low toxicity of CNMs toward the bioluminescent bacterium *Allivibrio*
 149 *fischeri* in Microtox assays (**Table 2**).

150 **Table 2** Toxicity of selected CNMs toward *Aliivibrio fischeri*.

Nanoparticle	Dimensions	Exposure time	EC ₅₀ [mg L ⁻¹]	Ref.
Fullerene soot (FS) ^a	N/A ^b	30 min	26	(Sanchís et al., 2016)
Fullerene C ₆₀	N/A	15 min	> 1	(Velzeboer et al., 2008)
Single-walled carbon nanotubes (SWCNTs)	$d = 1,2-1,5 \text{ nm}^c$ $l = 2-5 \mu\text{m}^d$	15 min	> 100	(Blaise et al., 2008)
Multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs)	$d = 12 \text{ nm}$ $l = 2.5-20 \mu\text{m}$	30 min	> 50	(Sanchís et al., 2016)
'Graphene' ('G')	30-50-layered	30 min	> 50	(Sanchís et al., 2016)

151 ^a Contents: 76% C₆₀, 22% C₇₀, ^b N/A = not applicable, ^c d – diameter, ^d l – length.

152 Nevertheless, substantial variation in ecotoxicological outcomes is evident, much of which can
 153 be attributed to differences in nanoparticle morphology, including shape, dimensionality, and
 154 aggregation behavior. 0D nanoforms such as fullerenes tend to exhibit comparatively higher
 155 toxicity, likely due to their small, spherical geometry, which enhances mobility and increases
 156 their biological accessibility. In contrast, 1D and 2D nanomaterials typically show lower
 157 adverse effects, as their elongated or planar structures, of a high specific surface area, promote
 158 the formation of larger aggregates that are less amenable to direct microbial interaction. This
 159 pattern suggests a general trend: more structurally complex and spatially extended CNMs tend
 160 to display reduced toxicity under short-term exposure conditions, whereas smaller, more mobile
 161 nanoparticles more readily interact with bacterial cells and therefore exhibit higher toxicity.

162 Potential mechanisms contributing to these effects include mechanical disruption of the cell
163 envelope and ensuing loss of membrane integrity, which can initiate oxidative stress and elevate
164 ROS levels, thereby amplifying cellular damage. Nonetheless, the limited ecotoxicological
165 evidence available for many CNM types highlights the necessity for further, systematic
166 research.

167 Aquatic environments constitute major receiving compartments for engineered nanomaterials
168 released from industrial processes as well as from domestic and consumer applications.
169 Wastewater discharge pathways and diffuse urban inputs contribute to the continuous transfer
170 of carbon nanomaterials into surface waters, making freshwater systems key compartment for
171 environmental exposure. Once introduced, nanomaterials undergo physicochemical
172 transformations – including aggregation, heteroaggregation with natural colloids, and
173 sedimentation – that critically determine their environmental fate and bioavailability (Lead et
174 al, 2018). CNMs interact with aquatic organisms in complex and often unpredictable ways.
175 Continuous exposure of lower-trophic-level organisms facilitates bioaccumulation and trophic
176 transfer, potentially propagating ecological impacts and risks to human health through the food
177 web (Chen et al., 2024) (Lalwani et al., 2016). A widely reported toxicity mechanism is
178 oxidative stress, whereby excessive ROS generation – arising from an imbalance between
179 production and antioxidant defenses and potentially exacerbated by mechanical damage to
180 cellular membranes – leads to protein and DNA damage, apoptosis or necrosis, and ultimately
181 organismal death (Li et al., 2012). Physical injuries may stem from the sharp-edged structure
182 of certain carbon nanomaterials (such as CNTs or graphene) (Akhavan et al., 2013). Moreover,
183 the fibrous morphology of certain CNMs can physically entangle cells or small aquatic
184 organisms, impairing mobility and feeding, underscoring the multifactorial and still poorly
185 predictable nature of CNM toxicity and the need for continued environmental research.

186 Taken together, the rapidly expanding diversity of 0D–3D CNMs and their highly variable
187 physicochemical and biological behaviors highlight the urgent need for integrated ecological
188 risk assessment. Despite increasing industrial use and environmental release, ecotoxicological
189 knowledge remains fragmented and strongly dependent on nanoform-specific properties. This
190 study addresses this gap by providing a systematic cross-trophic evaluation of well-defined
191 CNMs, identifying key determinants of biological response to support more informed
192 environmental risk management. To our knowledge, this is the first systematic 0D–3D cross-
193 dimensional ecotoxicity comparison across three aquatic trophic levels using uniformly
194 characterized CNMs under harmonized exposure conditions.

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206 **2. Materials and methods**

207 **2.1 Characterization of CNMs**

208 Key physicochemical properties of the selected CNMs are summarized in **Table 3**.

209 **Table 3** Characteristics of the herein studied CNMs.

Name, Producer	Symbol	D	Length [μm]	d [nm]	Purity [%]	Source
Fullerene soot (FS), Sigma-Aldrich	FS	0D	N/A ^a	N/A	7 ^b	(Józwiak et al., 2020)
Fullerene C ₆₀ , Modern Synthesis Technology	C ₆₀	0D	N/A	N/A	99.9	(MST)
Carbon quantum dots-Leu ^c , In-house	CQD-Leu	0D	N/A	1–5	N/A	(Kolanowska et al., 2022)
Carbon quantum dots-Phe ^d , In-house	CQD-Phe	0D	N/A	1–5	N/A	(Kolanowska et al., 2022)
SWCNT, Tuball	SWCNT	1D	5	2	85	(Józwiak et al., 2020)
MWCNT, Nanocyl NC7000	NC-MWCNT	1D	1.5	9.5	90	(Józwiak et al., 2020)
MWCNT, Nanocyl NC7000 (purified) ^e	NC-MWCNT-p	1D	1.5	9.5	90	(Józwiak et al., 2020)
MWCNT-COOH, Nanocyl NC7000	NC-MWCNT-COOH	1D	< 1.5	< 9.5	90	(Józwiak et al., 2020)
MWCNT, In-house	IN-MWCNT	1D	800	60	98	(Boncel et al., 2022)
MWCNT-COOH, In-house ^f	IN-MWCNT-COOH	1D	800	60	98	(Boncel et al., 2022)
Graphene G1, Levidian	G1	2D	N/A	0.3–1.7 ^g	98	(Kuziel et al., 2020)
Graphene G3, Levidian	G3	2D	N/A	1–5 ^g	98	(Kuziel et al., 2020)
Graphite, RMC Remacon	GR	3D	N/A	N/A	99.5	(RMC Remacon)
Nanodiamond, Carbodeon	ND	3D	N/A	4–6	97	(Carbodeon)

210 ^a Not applicable, ^b Contents: 76% C₆₀, 22% C₇₀, ^c Synthetic precursor – L-leucine, ^d Synthetic precursor – L-
 211 phenylalanine, ^e Free of Al₂O₃ and Fe, ^f Content of functional groups: -COOH 1.6 mmol g⁻¹, -OH 0.8 mmol g⁻¹, ^g
 212 Thickness.

213 **2.2 Preparation of CNM dispersions and suspensions**

214 To enable the use of the CNMs in these studies, conducted in an aquatic environment, a physical
 215 dispersion method (shaking) was applied allowing the preparation of CNM suspensions and
 216 dispersions. Moreover, the energy inputs accompanying the environmental introduction of
 217 CNMs are generally of the same order of magnitude as those generated by mechanical stirring.

218 Indeed, by applying mechanical energy, larger agglomerates were broken up, which evenly
219 dispersed CNMs in the aqueous medium. This technique is commonly used in ecotoxicity
220 assessments of materials and waste (Council Regulation (EC) No 440/2008, Council Regulation
221 (EU) 2017/997). CNM dispersions or suspensions were prepared from the stock dispersion or
222 suspensions at a concentration of 100 mg L⁻¹. Depending on the test, the stock suspensions or
223 dispersions were prepared in different aqueous media. The systems were prepared using an
224 automatic shaker with the following parameters: total shaking time 24 h, temperature 25 °C,
225 mixing intensity 150 rpm. For the ecotoxicity assessment, *Lemna minor* (OECD 221), *Daphnia*
226 *magna* (OECD 202), and *Allivibrio fischeri* (Microtox test) were applied.

227 **2.3 Growth inhibition test of *Lemna minor***

228 The phytotoxicity of CNMs was assessed using *L. minor* according to OECD guideline 221
229 (2006). The test was conducted in Steinberg medium (**Table S1**), which also served as the
230 control. CNM stock suspensions/dispersions (100 mg L⁻¹) were prepared in Steinberg medium
231 and diluted to final dispersion of 1 and 10 mg L⁻¹.

232 Aliquots (20 mL) were transferred to glass Petri dishes, each containing four *L. minor* colonies
233 (three fronds per colony; 12 fronds per dish). Three replicates were prepared per treatment. The
234 test was performed for 7 days under controlled conditions (22/19°C day/night, 12 h light:12 h
235 dark photoperiod, light intensity 10 klx).

236 At the end of the exposure, frond numbers were recorded and the mean growth rate (Eq. 1) and
237 percentage growth inhibition (Eq. 2) were calculated according to OECD 221.

$$238 \mu_{i-j} = \frac{\ln(N_j) - \ln(N_i)}{t} \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

239 where μ_{i-j} is the mean growth rate from time i to j , $N_{i(j)}$ is the number of fronds at time $i(j)$, and
240 t is the time interval between i and j (days);

$$241 \quad \%I_r = \frac{\mu_C - \mu_T}{\mu_C} \times 100 \quad (\text{Eq. 2})$$

242 where $\%I_r$ is the percentage inhibition of the mean growth rate, μ_C is the mean μ value for the
243 control sample, and μ_T is the mean μ value for the test sample. When possible, EC_{50} values
244 (50% growth inhibition) were determined, and toxicity units (TU) were calculated.

245 **2.4 Immobilization test of *Daphnia magna***

246 Acute toxicity to *D. magna* was evaluated following OECD guideline 202 (2004) using the
247 Daphtoxkit F microbiotest (Tigret, Poland). The test medium consisted of aerated good quality
248 drinking water (pH=7.6, specific electrical conductivity at 25°C = 778 $\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$, total hardness
249 = 359 mg L^{-1} , turbidity $< 0.20 \pm 0.06$ NTU) and served as the control. *D. magna* ephippia were
250 reactivated for 72 h under controlled conditions (22/19°C day/night, 12 h light:12 h dark), and
251 neonates were fed with spirulina 2 h prior to the exposure (Grintzalis et al., 2017).

252 CNM stock dispersions were prepared in the test medium, ensuring homogeneous particle
253 distribution, and subsequently subjected to two-fold serial dilution (100–6.25% of the initial
254 dispersion). Five neonates were placed in each well (5 mL), with four replicates per treatment.
255 The number of *D. magna* individuals was reduced to five per well following the miniaturized
256 adaptation of OECD Test No. 202, as demonstrated to provide comparable mortality outcomes
257 without statistically significant differences from the standard design (Grintzalis et al., 2017).
258 This modification allowed a substantial reduction in test organism use, medium volume, and
259 test material consumption while maintaining assay reliability. The approach aligns with the 3R
260 principle, particularly the Reduction strategy, by minimizing animal use without compromising
261 data quality. The test was conducted for 48 h at 25°C in the dark.

262 Immobilization was recorded after 24 and 48 h; organisms were considered immobilized if no
263 movement was observed after gentle agitation. Immobilization percentages were calculated
264 according to Eq. 3. EC₅₀ values and toxicity units (TU) were determined where applicable.

$$265 \quad \%I = \frac{C - T}{C} \times 100 \quad (\text{Eq. 3})$$

266 where $\%I$ is the percentage of immobilization, C is the number of live organisms in the control
267 sample, and T is the number of live organisms in the test sample.

268 **2.5 Bioluminescence inhibition test of *Aliivibrio fischeri***

269 The toxicity of CNMs was assessed using the Microtox assay with *Aliivibrio fischeri*, in
270 accordance with ISO 11348-3 and the WET procedure. Lyophilized bacteria were reactivated
271 following the manufacturer's instructions (Modern Water Ltd, UK). A 2% NaCl solution was
272 used as the diluent and control.

273 To avoid interference from light scattering, only filtrates of CNM suspensions were tested.
274 Filtration was performed using paper filters, and NaCl was added to each filtrate to achieve a
275 final concentration of 2%. Serial dilutions (100–6.25%, dilution factor 2) were prepared in
276 Microtox cuvettes; three replicates were analyzed per sample.

277 After adding the bacterial suspension, bioluminescence was measured at 490 nm following 15-
278 min exposure. Luminescence inhibition was calculated using the gamma model (Eq. 4, 5).

$$279 \quad \Gamma_T = \frac{I_C - I_T}{I_T} = \frac{I_C}{I_T} - 1 \quad (\text{Eq. 4})$$

280 where Γ_T is the gamma value of the test sample after 15 min of exposure, I_C is the luminescence
281 intensity of the control sample after 15 min of exposure, and I_T is the luminescence intensity of
282 the test sample after 15 min of exposure.

283
$$\%I_r = \frac{100 \times I_T}{1 + I_T} \quad (\text{Eq. 5})$$

284 where $\%I_r$ is the percentage of luminescence inhibition.

285 For non-transparent samples, color correction was applied following Ashworth et al. (2010)
286 (Eq. 6–8).

287
$$I_{TC} = \frac{I_C \times T_T - I_T}{I_{TC}} = \frac{I_C \times T_T}{I_{TC}} - 1 \quad (\text{Eq. 6})$$

288 where T_T is the transmittance coefficient of the tested sample.

289
$$T_T = \frac{1 - e^{-A_T}}{A_T} \quad (\text{Eq. 7})$$

290 where A_T is the absorbance coefficient of the tested sample.

291
$$A_T = 1.75 \times Abs_T \quad (\text{Eq. 8})$$

292 where Abs_T is the absorbance of the tested sample at a wavelength of 490 nm.

293 To quantify nanoparticle content in the filtrates, dry mass analysis was performed after filtration
294 and drying at 105°C. Based on luminescence inhibition, EC_{50} and TU values were calculated
295 when possible.

296 **2.6 Statistical analysis methods**

297 Statistical analyses were performed using Statistica v.13.3 (StatSoft Inc.). Normality of data
298 distribution was verified using the Shapiro-Wilk test and homogeneity of variance was assessed
299 with the Brown-Forsythe test. For normally distributed data with equal variances, the Student's
300 t -test (two groups) or one-way ANOVA (multiple groups) was applied. When assumptions of

301 normality were not met, the Mann-Whitney U test was used. The significance level was set at
302 $\alpha = 0.05$. Differences were considered statistically significant when $p < 0.05$.

303 Median effective concentrations (EC_{50}/IC_{50}) were determined by graphical interpolation.

304 TU was calculated according to Persoone's classification as (Eq. 9) (Persoone et al, 2003):

305
$$TU = 100/EC_{50}(IC_{50}) \quad \text{Eq. (9)}$$

306 TU provide a standardized framework for categorizing the severity of toxic effects into five
307 toxicity classes. TU values below 0.4 indicate no acute toxicity, whereas values between 0.4
308 and 1 correspond to low toxicity. Moderate toxicity is assigned to the range of 1–10, whereas
309 values of 10–100 denote high toxicity. When TU values exceed 100, the exposure is classified
310 as exhibiting extreme toxicity (Persoone et al., 2003). If the toxic effect of the tested sample
311 prevents the calculation of EC_{50} or IC_{50} values (the effect is 10–49%), the TU is calculated
312 according to Eq. 10.

313
$$TU = 0.02 \times EC_{50}(IC_{50}) \quad \text{Eq. (10)}$$

314 where E is the highest observed effect [%] of the tested sample.

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320 3. Results and discussion

321 Fourteen (14) types of CNMs were included in the analysis, comprising ten (10) commercially
322 sourced materials and four (4) synthesized in-house, all encompassing a range of
323 dimensionalities and physicochemical properties. The tested materials included fullerene soot
324 (FS, a mixture of C₆₀ and C₇₀ fullerenes), pristine fullerene C₆₀, two types CQDs synthesized
325 from aliphatic (CQD-Leu) *versus* aromatic (CQD-Phe) amino acids, SWCNTs, MWCNTs of a
326 variety of morphologies and surface chemistries such as covalent polar functionalization with
327 COOH groups, graphene (G), graphene oxide (GR), and nanodiamonds (ND). The selection of
328 these CNMs was guided primarily by their diversity in dimensionality, morphology, and surface
329 characteristics, as well as their relevance to commonly produced and potentially
330 environmentally encountered carbon nanomaterials.

331 SEM analysis revealed pronounced differences in the micro- and nanomorphology of the
332 investigated CNMs, reflecting their dimensionality, synthesis routes, and surface
333 functionalization, all of which are highly relevant for ecotoxicological behavior (**Fig. S1**). 0D
334 CNMs, including FS, C₆₀, and both CQDs exhibited predominantly quasi-spherical
335 morphologies with varying degrees of aggregation and crystallinity. FS and C₆₀ formed
336 compact agglomerates, indicative of strong van der Waals interactions, whereas CQDs
337 appeared as finer, densely packed crystalline clusters. In contrast, 1D CNMs – SWCNTs and
338 MWCNTs – displayed characteristic aligned, fibrous, and partially entangled networks. Pristine
339 MWCNTs showed dense bundles and rope-like aggregates, while purified and carboxyl-
340 functionalized variants exhibited reduced bundling and more open structures, suggesting
341 greater effective surface area. At low magnification, thinner Nanocyl NC7000 MWCNTs
342 emerged as spheroids while high-aspect-ratio SWCNTs and MWCNTs preferentially formed
343 fibrils. Such morphological changes are known to modulate cellular interactions, including

344 membrane adhesion and internalization. 2D graphene-based materials, G1 and G3, presented
345 as thin, crumpled sheets with lateral stacking, whereas 3D graphite (GR) retained a compact,
346 layered morphology at the microscale.

347 The ecotoxicological assessment employed a combination of acute and chronic toxicity tests.
348 The encompassing a broad spectrum of CNM types enabled a nuanced analysis of how
349 structural and physicochemical variations influence interactions with aquatic environments and
350 organisms, thereby facilitating a more detailed and mechanistic understanding of CNM
351 ecotoxicity. The results of the ecotoxicity tests on *Lemna minor* are presented in **Fig. 2** (*upper*
352 *panel*) (and **Table S2**).

353

354 **Fig. 2** Upper panel: Ecotoxicity of CNMs toward *L. minor*. (A) 0D: a – no statistically
 355 significant differences between FS, C₆₀, and CQD2 (ANOVA test), b – statistically significant
 356 differences between CQD1 and FS, C₆₀, and CQD2 (ANOVA test), c – statistically significant

357 differences between CQD1 and CQD2 (Student's t-test).; **(B)** 1D: a – no statistically significant
358 differences between NC-MWCNT-p and NC-MWCNT (Student's t-test), b – statistically
359 significant differences between NC-MWCNT-p and NC-MWCNT *versus* NC-MWCNT-
360 COOH, IN-MWCNT, and IN-MWCNT-COOH (ANOVA test), c – no statistically significant
361 differences between SWCNT and NC-MWCNT-p, NC-MWCNT-COOH, IN-MWCNT, and
362 IN-MWCNT-COOH (ANOVA test), d – statistically significant differences between SWCNT
363 and NC-MWCNT (Student's t-test).; **(C)** 2D: a – no statistically significant differences between
364 G1 and G3 (Student's t-test); **(D)** 3D: a – no statistically significant differences between G1 and
365 G3 (Student's t-test). *Bottom panel: L. minor* after 7 days of exposure to CQD-Leu (photograph
366 taken with a digital camera, 1.5× magnification); the arrows indicate chlorosis.

367 Among the 0D CNMs, CQD-Leu exhibited the highest toxicity (TU = 1.53), corresponding to
368 toxicity class III. In comparison, FS (TU = 0.81), C₆₀ (TU = 0.95), and CQD-Phe (TU = 0.57)
369 showed significantly lower toxicity, assigned as class II. Statistical analysis confirmed
370 significant differences between CQD-Leu and CQD-Phe. Among CQDs investigated, the
371 significantly higher toxicity observed for CQD-Leu compared with CQD-Phe can be
372 rationalized on the basis of their distinct surface chemistry and resultant physicochemical
373 interactions with biological systems. CQDs synthesized from different amino acid precursors
374 inherently incorporate structural moieties reflective of the side chains of those amino acids,
375 which in turn influence surface functional group composition, charge distribution,
376 hydrophobicity, and colloidal stability – all established determinants of nanomaterial-organism
377 interaction and toxicity. CQDs consist of a graphitic core surrounded by an amorphous shell
378 bearing polar and non-polar functionalities that originate from the precursor molecules and the
379 synthesis conditions (Kolanowska et al., 2022). Amino acids with aliphatic side chains, such as
380 leucine, may contribute to a higher proportion of hydrophobic, amine-rich, and redox-active
381 surface sites, which can increase non-specific interactions with lipid membranes and proteins

382 of exposed organisms, possibly facilitating membrane perturbation and enhanced uptake (Wang
383 et al., 2011). By contrast, aromatic side chains such as that in phenylalanine may lead to π - π
384 stacking and enhanced structural rigidity of the CQD surface layer, which can modulate
385 colloidal behavior and reduce bioavailability in aqueous media at environmentally relevant
386 concentrations. Despite the measured concentrations of primary amino (-NH₂) and carboxyl (-
387 COOH) groups in CQD-Leu ([NH₂] = 3.340 ± 0.045 mmol g⁻¹, [COOH] = 1.660 ± 0.008 mmol
388 g⁻¹) versus CQD-Phe ([NH₂] = 4.890 ± 0.238 mmol g⁻¹, [COOH] = 1.132 ± 0.104 mmol g⁻¹),
389 the intrinsic basicity of amino groups in aliphatic *quasi*-amino acids is substantially higher than
390 in aromatic counterparts due to the absence of conjugation with the aromatic π -system, thereby
391 enhancing their propensity for electrostatic interactions with positively charged cellular
392 membranes. In summary, the differential toxicity observed here likely reflects precursor-
393 dependent surface chemistry effects that modulate CQD interaction with test organisms,
394 affecting uptake, oxidative stress induction, and ultimately toxicological outcomes.

395 The observed patterns of toxicity among the 1D CNMs are consistent with established structure-
396 activity relationships reported in the literature, where surface chemistry, dispersion state, and
397 effective surface area strongly influence biological responses. Nanocyl-MWCNT and Nanocyl-
398 MWCNT-purified – both exhibiting moderately toxic responses (TU~1.12–1.25) and
399 statistically higher toxicity than their carboxylated (NC-MWCNT-COOH) and longer
400 counterparts – likely owe their increased bioactivity to a combination of greater hydrophobic
401 surface character, higher agglomeration propensity, and unmodified surface defect structures
402 that enhance organismal interaction. Pristine or purified MWCNTs typically retain graphitic
403 surfaces with fewer oxygen-containing groups, which facilitates strong hydrophobic
404 interactions with cell membranes and environmental interfaces, potentially leading to increased
405 cellular uptake and membrane perturbation compared to oxidized analogues (Holdbrook et al.,
406 2021). Carboxylation is widely reported to improve aqueous dispersibility and reduce intrinsic

407 bioactivity by increasing hydrophilicity and electrostatic repulsion, thereby mitigating direct
408 membrane interactions and lowering toxicity endpoints in cellular and whole-organism models
409 (Sweeney et al., 2016). Specifically, MWCNT-COOH have been shown to provoke reduced
410 inflammatory and cytotoxic responses relative to purified MWCNTs, attributed to alterations in
411 surface chemistry that inhibit recognition and uptake by biological barriers and attenuate
412 oxidative stress pathways (Singh et al., 2012).

413 Among 2D CNMs, G1 (TU = 1.34) and G3 (TU = 1.20) showed moderate toxicity, with no
414 statistically significant difference between them. Similarly, 3D CNMs, ND (TU = 0.50) and GR
415 (TU = 0.40), exhibited moderate toxicity, with differences also not reaching statistical
416 significance.

417 Among the fourteen tested CNMs, CQD-Leu exhibited the highest toxicity toward *Lemna*
418 *minor* ($EC_{50} = 65.2 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$, corresponding to TU = 1.53), as confirmed by statistical analysis.
419 **Fig. 2 (bottom panel)** shows observations of *Lemna minor* after 7 days of exposure to CQD-
420 Leu, which exhibited the highest toxicity toward this organism. At the highest concentration
421 tested (100 mg L^{-1}), chlorosis was observed, indicating a loss of the chlorophyll. No such
422 changes were detected in the control sample and lower concentrations CQD-Leu.

423 The results of the ecotoxicity tests on *Daphnia magna* are presented in **Fig. 3 (upper panel)**
424 (and **Table S3**). Statistical analysis indicated that, among all tested CNMs, IN-MWCNT-COOH
425 exhibited the highest overall toxicity toward *D. magna*, with TU values increasing markedly
426 from $TU_{(24 \text{ h})} = 1.48$ (class III) to $TU_{(48 \text{ h})} = 17.24$ (class IV), corresponding to an $EC_{50(48 \text{ h})}$ of
427 5.8 mg L^{-1} . This pronounced time-dependent toxicity distinguishes IN-MWCNT-COOH from
428 all other nanomaterials investigated and suggests a mechanism governed by a unique
429 combination of morphology and dispersibility. Specifically, IN-MWCNT-COOH combines a
430 high aspect ratio (long nanotubes) with sufficient aqueous dispersibility imparted by carboxyl
431 functionalization, enabling efficient ingestion and internalization by *D. magna*. Optical

432 micrographs after 48 h of exposure (**Fig. 3**, *bottom panel*) clearly demonstrate accumulation of
433 these nanotubes within the digestive tract, where their length likely promotes physical clogging
434 and retention, impairing gut function. Once internalized, their elongated morphology renders
435 them poorly amenable to metabolic processing or elimination, leading to progressive adverse
436 effects with prolonged exposure. The observations revealed black, globular structures
437 morphologically consistent with aggregates of nanotubes.

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448 **Fig. 3** *Upper panel:* Ecotoxicity of CNMs toward *D. magna* (A) 0D: a – no statistically
449 significant differences between FS, C₆₀, CQD2, and CQD1 (ANOVA test), b – no statistically
450 significant differences between 24 h and 48 h (Student's t-test); (B) 1D: a – no statistically
451 significant differences among SWCNT, NC-MWCNT-p, NC-MWCNT, NC-MWCNT-COOH,
452 IN-MWCNT, and IN-MWCNT-COOH after 24 h (ANOVA test), b – no statistically significant
453 differences among SWCNT, NC-MWCNT-p, NC-MWCNT, NC-MWCNT-COOH, and IN-
454 MWCNT after 48 h (ANOVA test), c – statistically significant differences between IN-
455 MWCNT-COOH at 24 h and 48 h (Student's t-test). (C) 2D: a – no statistically significant
456 differences between G1 (24 h) and G3 (24 h) (Mann–Whitney U test), b – statistically
457 significant differences between G1 (48 h) and G3 (48 h) (Mann–Whitney U test), c – no
458 statistically significant differences between 24 h and 48 h (Mann–Whitney U test), d –
459 statistically significant differences between 24 h and 48 h (Mann–Whitney U test). (D) 3D: a –
460 no statistically significant differences between GR (24 h) and ND (24 h) (Mann–Whitney U
461 test), b – no statistically significant differences between GR (48 h) and ND (48 h) (Mann–
462 Whitney U test), c – no statistically significant differences between 24 h and 48 h (Student's t-
463 test). *Bottom panel:* *Daphnia magna* after 48 h of exposure to different concentrations of IN-
464 MWCNT-COOH (light microscopy, 40× magnification); the arrows indicate sites of aggregate
465 accumulation.

466 These aggregates were primarily localized in the digestive tract and also along the posterior
467 spine. Starting from a concentration of 25 mg L⁻¹ and above, the accumulation became
468 continuous along these pathways. Also, at this concentration, the spine – which serves primarily
469 for defense and swimming stabilization – was extensively coated with nanotube agglomerates.
470 Such coverage can impair mobility, induce substantial physiological stress, and interfere with
471 feeding and excretion, potentially leading to mortality as observed for the highest concentration
472 of IN-MWCNT-COOH. No comparable aggregates were observed in the control samples.

473 In contrast, other CNMs appear to fall into two less harmful extremes: materials that are long
474 but poorly dispersible tend to form aggregates that limit bioavailability and ingestion, whereas
475 fully dispersible, shorter, or lower-aspect-ratio CNMs (*e.g.*, 0D materials such as FS, C₆₀, CQD-
476 Leu, and CQD-Phe, all class II at both 24 and 48 h) are more readily incorporated into metabolic
477 or clearance pathways, at least within the tested exposure duration. Similarly, 2D and 3D CNMs
478 exhibited moderate toxicity (class II), with time-dependent effects observed only for specific
479 materials (*e.g.*, G3), likely reflecting slower accumulation processes rather than acute physical
480 interference. Collectively, these results highlight that the coexistence of high aspect ratio and
481 environmental dispersibility is a critical determinant of ecotoxicological hazard, explaining
482 why IN-MWCNT-COOH emerged as the most toxic CNM in this study.

483 The results of the toxicity tests conducted with *Aliivibrio fischeri* are presented in **Fig. 4**.
484 Statistical analysis of the 0D CNMs revealed no significant differences in toxicity toward *A.*
485 *fischeri* among FS (TU = 0.44), C₆₀ (TU = 1.08), CQD-Leu (TU = 0.98), and CQD-Phe (TU =
486 0.54), resulting in all being categorized within toxicity class II. This general uniformity aligns
487 with the broader consensus that 0D CNMs, due to their limited aspect ratio and often reduced
488 ability to physically interact with or penetrate bacterial cell envelopes, tend to elicit moderate
489 acute effects in luminescence inhibition assays, unless pronounced surface reactivity or
490 contaminant artifacts are present. Comprehensive reviews have documented that C₆₀ derivatives
491 and CQDs typically induce low-to-moderate responses in bacterial assays, with toxicological
492 outcomes strongly modulated by surface functionalization and aggregation state in exposure
493 media (Abdolahpur Monikh et al., 2023). MWCNTs exhibited moderate toxicity (toxicity class
494 III), with no statistically significant differences among the various MWCNT samples tested. By
495 contrast, SWCNT (TU = 0.21) showed no measurable toxicity toward *A. fischeri* – a statistically
496 significant distinction. This divergence is consistent with literature highlighting that dispersion
497 behavior and effective bioavailability, rather than intrinsic dimensionality alone, dictate acute

498 bacterial toxicity: well-dispersed MWCNT bundles present greater surface area and interactive
 499 interfaces that can disrupt membrane integrity or adsorb critical nutrients, whereas poorly
 500 dispersed SWCNT aggregates may sediment rapidly and thus reduce effective contact with
 501 planktonic bacteria under the Microtox conditions.

502

503 **Fig. 4** Toxicity of CNMs toward *V. fischeri*. (A) 0D: a – no statistically significant differences
 504 between FS, C₆₀, CQD1, and CQD2 (ANOVA test); (B) 1D: a – statistically significant
 505 differences between SWCNT and NC-MWCNT-p, NC-MWCNT, NC-MWCNT-COOH, IN-
 506 MWCNT, and IN-MWCNT-COOH (ANOVA test), b – no statistically significant differences
 507 among NC-MWCNT-p, NC-MWCNT, NC-MWCNT-COOH, IN-MWCNT, and IN-MWCNT-
 508 COOH (ANOVA test); (C) 2D: a – statistically significant differences between G1 and G3

509 (Student's t-test); **(D)** 3D: a – statistically significant differences between GR and ND (Student's
510 t-test).

511 Previous studies have similarly reported that SWCNTs, especially in the absence of strong
512 dispersants, form large agglomerates that limit exposure in bacterial assays, resulting in
513 negligible luminescence inhibition (Klaine et al., 2008) (Gottschalk et al., 2009).

514 For 2D CNMs, G3 (TU = 1.37) demonstrated significantly higher toxicity than G1 (TU = 0.85).
515 Consequently, G3 was classified as toxicity class III, whereas G1 remained within class II. This
516 distinction can be understood in terms of graphene thickness and surface chemical features,
517 which affect colloidal stability and interaction with bacterial cell surfaces. Thinner graphene
518 flakes tend more to agglomerate (Kuziel et al., 2020), while nanographene derivatives with
519 increased defect densities, edge sites, or functional groups tend to exhibit higher dispersibility
520 in water, as opposed to the pristine graphene. Similar trend was reported in recent
521 comprehensive reviews (Fadeel et al., 2018) and original investigations on graphene oxides
522 (Krasoń et al., 2024).

523 Statistical analysis of 3D CNMs indicated no significant difference in toxicity between graphite
524 (GR, TU = 0.92) and nanodiamonds (ND, TU = 1.34), with GR assigned to toxicity class II and
525 ND to class III. Such outcomes are consistent with the understanding that 3D CNMs display
526 intermediate bioactivity, largely dependent on surface chemistry, defect structures, and
527 dispersion behavior in aqueous media. NDs, owing to their high surface area as well as sharp
528 and rigid edges may exhibit elevated interactions with bacterial cells relative to bulk graphite,
529 resulting in modestly higher toxicity, as observed in recent nanoecotoxicological assessments
530 (Zhang et al., 2017).

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533 **Conclusions**

534 The present results demonstrate that the ecotoxicity of CNMs is highly trophic-level dependent,
535 reflecting a complex interplay between organismal biology and CNM physicochemical
536 attributes, including morphology, surface chemistry, dispersibility, size, and aggregation
537 behavior. Among the tested organisms, the highest sensitivity was observed in the crustacean
538 *Daphnia magna*, a key consumer species, for which all investigated CNMs were classified as
539 at least moderately toxic. Notably, IN-MWCNT-COOH emerged as particularly hazardous (IV
540 class) under prolonged exposure, exhibiting high toxicity after 48 h ($EC_{50(48\text{ h})} = 5.8\text{ mg L}^{-1}$;
541 $TU_{(48\text{ h})} = 17.24$). This pronounced effect is most plausibly attributed to the bioaccumulation of
542 high-aspect-ratio yet water-dispersible nanotubes within the digestive tract, where their
543 elongated geometry promotes retention and impedes elimination. As an actively swimming
544 filter-feeding organism, *D. magna* is especially vulnerable to well-suspended CNMs, resulting
545 in sustained internal exposure. In contrast, the primary producer *Lemna minor* was most
546 affected by well-dispersed, nanoscale carbon particles, particularly CQD-Leu ($EC_{50} = 65.2\text{ mg}$
547 L^{-1} ; $TU = 1.53$), with chlorosis and disruption of photosynthetic processes identified as likely
548 drivers of toxicity. The decomposer organism *Aliivibrio fischeri* exhibited comparatively lower
549 sensitivity, underscoring the role of both exposure pathways and organism-specific uptake
550 mechanisms in shaping toxicological outcomes. Collectively, these findings highlight that no
551 single CNM property governs ecological hazard, but rather that toxicity emerges from the
552 dynamic interaction between nanomaterial design and trophic-level biology. These findings
553 support the prioritization of high-aspect-ratio, environmentally dispersible carbon nanotubes in
554 regulatory frameworks addressing advanced carbon nanomaterials.

555 Looking forward, ecotoxicological assessment of CNMs should increasingly shift toward long-
556 term, multigenerational, and food-web-relevant exposure scenarios, and it is likely that future

557 studies will reveal cumulative and indirect effects – such as trophic transfer and chronic
558 physiological impairment – that remain largely undetectable in shorter-term assays.

559

560 **Declaration of competing interest**

561 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal
562 relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

563

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572

573 **Literature**

574 Abdolahpur Monikh, F., Peijnenburg, W., Oomen, A.G., Valsami-Jones, E., Stone, V.,
575 Kortet, R., Akkanen, J., Zhang, P., Kekäläinen, J., Sevcu, A., Kukkonen, J.V.K., 2023.
576 “Advanced materials” and the challenges on the horizon for testing their
577 (eco)toxicity and assessing their hazard. *Environ. Sci. Adv.* 2, 162–170.
578 <https://doi.org/10.1039/D2VA00128D>
579 Akhavan, O., Ghaderi, E., Emamy, H., Akhavan, F., 2013. Genotoxicity of graphene
580 nanoribbons in human mesenchymal stem cells. *Carbon* 54, 419–431.
581 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbon.2012.11.058>
582 Blaise, C., Gagné, F., Férard, J.F., Eullaffroy, P., 2008. Ecotoxicity of selected nano-
583 materials to aquatic organisms. *Environ. Toxicol.* 23, 591–598.
584 <https://doi.org/10.1002/tox.20402>

585 Boncel, S., Herman, A.P., Budniok, S., Jędrzyak, R.G., Jakóbiak-Kolon, A., Skepper, J.N.,
586 Müller, K.H., 2016. In Vitro Targeting and Selective Killing of T47D Breast Cancer
587 Cells by Purpurin and 5-Fluorouracil Anchored to Magnetic CNTs: Nitrene-Based
588 Functionalization versus Uptake, Cytotoxicity, and Intracellular Fate. ACS
589 Biomater. Sci. Eng. 2, 1273–1285.
590 <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsbiomaterials.6b00197>

591 Boncel, S., Jędrzyak, R.G., Czerw, M., Kolanowska, A., Blacha, A.W., Imielski, M.,
592 Józwiak, B., Dzida, M.H., Greer, H.F., Sobotnicki, A., 2022. Paintable Carbon
593 Nanotube Coating-Based Textronics for Sustained Holter-Type
594 Electrocardiography. ACS Appl. Nano Mater. 5, 15762–15774.
595 <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsanm.2c03904>

596 Boncel, S., Kyzioł-Komosińska, J., Krzyżewska, I., Czupioł, J., 2015. Interactions of
597 carbon nanotubes with aqueous/aquatic media containing organic/inorganic
598 contaminants and selected organisms of aquatic ecosystems – A review.
599 Chemosphere 136, 211–221.
600 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2015.04.095>

601 Boncel, S., Pluta, A., Skonieczna, M., Gondela, A., Maciejewska, B., Herman, A.P.,
602 Jędrzyak, R.G., Budniok, S., Komędera, K., Błachowski, A., Walczak, K.Z., 2017.
603 Hybrids of Iron-Filled Multiwall Carbon Nanotubes and Anticancer Agents as
604 Potential Magnetic Drug Delivery Systems: In Vitro Studies against Human
605 Melanoma, Colon Carcinoma, and Colon Adenocarcinoma. J. Nanomater. 2017,
606 1262309. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2017/1262309>

607 Cano, A.M., Maul, J.D., Saed, M., Shah, S.A., Green, M.J., Cañas-Carrell, J.E., 2017.
608 Bioaccumulation, stress, and swimming impairment in *Daphnia magna* exposed
609 to multiwalled carbon nanotubes, graphene, and graphene oxide. Environ.
610 Toxicol. Chem. 36, 2199–2204. <https://doi.org/10.1002/etc.3754>

611 Carbodeon, n.d. Nanodiamond.

612 Chen, A., Wang, B., Feng, Q., Wang, R., 2024. Potential toxicity of carbonaceous
613 nanomaterials on aquatic organisms and their alleviation strategies: A review.
614 Ecotoxicol. Environ. Saf. 285, 117019.
615 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoenv.2024.117019>

616 Devadasu, V.R., Bhardwaj, V., Kumar, M.N.V.R., 2013. Can Controversial
617 Nanotechnology Promise Drug Delivery? Chem. Rev. 113, 1686–1735.
618 <https://doi.org/10.1021/cr300047q>

619 Fadeel, B., Bussy, C., Merino, S., Vázquez, E., Flahaut, E., Mouchet, F., Evariste, L.,
620 Gauthier, L., Koivisto, A.J., Vogel, U., Martín, C., Delogu, L.G., Buerki-Thurnherr, T.,
621 Wick, P., Beloin-Saint-Pierre, D., Hischier, R., Pelin, M., Candotto Carniel, F.,
622 Tretiach, M., Cesca, F., Benfenati, F., Scaini, D., Ballerini, L., Kostarelos, K., Prato,
623 M., Bianco, A., 2018. Safety Assessment of Graphene-Based Materials: Focus on
624 Human Health and the Environment. ACS Nano 12, 10582–10620.
625 <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.nano.8b04758>

626 Gamoń, F., Ziemińska-Buczyńska, A., Łukowiec, D., Tomaszewski, M., 2023. Ecotoxicity
627 of selected carbon-based nanomaterials. Int. J. Environ. Sci. Technol. 20, 10153–
628 10162. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13762-022-04692-w>

629 Gottschalk, F., Sonderer, T., Scholz, R.W., Nowack, B., 2009. Modeled Environmental
630 Concentrations of Engineered Nanomaterials (TiO₂, ZnO, Ag, CNT, Fullerenes) for

631 Different Regions. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 43, 9216–9222.
632 <https://doi.org/10.1021/es9015553>

633 Grintzalis, K., Dai, W., Panagiotidis, K., Belavgeni, A., Viant, M.R., 2017. Miniaturising
634 acute toxicity and feeding rate measurements in *Daphnia magna*. *Ecotoxicol.*
635 *Environ. Saf.* 139, 352–357. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoenv.2017.02.002>

636 Guo, L., Von Dem Bussche, A., Buechner, M., Yan, A., Kane, A.B., Hurt, R.H., 2008.
637 Adsorption of Essential Micronutrients by Carbon Nanotubes and the
638 Implications for Nanotoxicity Testing. *Small* 4, 721–727.
639 <https://doi.org/10.1002/smll.200700754>

640 Gusain, M., Sindhu, M., Tewary, A., 2025. Advanced carbon nanomaterials for high-
641 performance energy storage technologies. *Nanotechnol.* 8, 100283.
642 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nxnano.2025.100283>

643 Holdbrook, D.A., Marzinek, J.K., Boncel, S., Boags, A., Tan, Y.S., Huber, R.G., Verma, C.S.,
644 Bond, P.J., 2021. The nanotube express: Delivering a stapled peptide to the cell
645 surface. *J. Colloid Interface Sci.* 604, 670–679.
646 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcis.2021.07.023>

647 Hughes, K.J., Iyer, K.A., Bird, R.E., Ivanov, J., Banerjee, S., Georges, G., Zhou, Q.A., 2024.
648 Review of Carbon Nanotube Research and Development: Materials and Emerging
649 Applications. *ACS Appl. Nano Mater.* 7, 18695–18713.
650 <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsanm.4c02721>

651 Józwiak, B., Dzido, G., Zorębski, E., Kolanowska, A., Jędrysiak, R., Dziadosz, J., Libera,
652 M., Boncel, S., Dzida, M., 2020. Remarkable Thermal Conductivity Enhancement
653 in Carbon-Based Ionanofluids: Effect of Nanoparticle Morphology. *ACS Appl.*
654 *Mater. Interfaces* 12, 38113–38123. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsam.0c09752>

655 Klaine, S.J., Alvarez, P.J.J., Batley, G.E., Fernandes, T.F., Handy, R.D., Lyon, D.Y.,
656 Mahendra, S., McLaughlin, M.J., Lead, J.R., 2008. Nanomaterials in the
657 environment: Behavior, fate, bioavailability, and effects. *Environ. Toxicol. Chem.*
658 27, 1825–1851. <https://doi.org/10.1897/08-090.1>

659 Kolanowska, A., Dzido, G., Krzywiecki, M., Tomczyk, M.M., Łukowiec, D., Ruczka, S.,
660 Boncel, S., 2022. Carbon Quantum Dots from Amino Acids Revisited: Survey of
661 Renewable Precursors toward High Quantum-Yield Blue and Green
662 Fluorescence. *ACS Omega* 7, 41165–41176.
663 <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsomega.2c04751>

664 Krasoń, M.Z., Paradowska, A., Boncel, S., Lejawa, M., Fronczek, M., Śliwka, J., Nożyński,
665 J., Bogus, P., Hrapkiewicz, T., Czamara, K., Kaczor, A., Radomski, M.W., 2024.
666 Graphene Oxide Significantly Modifies Cardiac Parameters and Coronary
667 Endothelial Reactivity in Healthy and Hypertensive Rat Hearts Ex Vivo. *ACS*
668 *Omega* 9, 28397–28411. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsomega.4c02291>

669 Kuziel, A.W., Milowska, K.Z., Chau, P.-L., Boncel, S., Koziol, K.K., Yahya, N., Payne, M.C.,
670 2020. The True Amphipathic Nature of Graphene Flakes: A Versatile 2D Stabilizer.
671 *Adv Mater.*

672 Lalwani, G., D’Agati, M., Khan, A.M., Sitharaman, B., 2016. Toxicology of graphene-based
673 nanomaterials. *Adv. Drug Deliv. Rev.* 105, 109–144.
674 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.addr.2016.04.028>

675 Lead, J.R., Batley, G.E., Alvarez, P.J.J., Croteau, M., Handy, R.D., McLaughlin, M.J., Judy,
676 J.D., Schirmer, K., 2018. Nanomaterials in the environment: Behavior, fate,

677 bioavailability, and effects—An updated review. *Environ. Toxicol. Chem.* 37,
678 2029–2063. <https://doi.org/10.1002/etc.4147>

679 Li, Y., Liu, Y., Fu, Y., Wei, T., Le Guyader, L., Gao, G., Liu, R.-S., Chang, Y.-Z., Chen, C.,
680 2012. The triggering of apoptosis in macrophages by pristine graphene through
681 the MAPK and TGF-beta signaling pathways. *Biomaterials* 33, 402–411.
682 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biomaterials.2011.09.091>

683 Lv, X., Huang, B., Zhu, X., Jiang, Y., Chen, B., Tao, Y., Zhou, J., Cai, Z., 2017. Mechanisms
684 underlying the acute toxicity of fullerene to *Daphnia magna*: Energy acquisition
685 restriction and oxidative stress. *Water Res.* 123, 696–703.
686 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2017.07.023>

687 Mendonça, E., Diniz, M., Silva, L., Peres, I., Castro, L., Correia, J.B., Picado, A., 2011.
688 Effects of diamond nanoparticle exposure on the internal structure and
689 reproduction of *Daphnia magna*. *J. Hazard. Mater.* 186, 265–271.
690 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2010.10.115>

691 MST, n.d. Fullerene C60.

692 Persoone, G., Marsalek, B., Blinova, I., Törökne, A., Zarina, D., Manusadzianas, L.,
693 Nalecz-Jawecki, G., Tofan, L., Stepanova, N., Tothova, L., Kolar, B., 2003. A
694 practical and user-friendly toxicity classification system with microbiotests for
695 natural waters and wastewaters. *Environ. Toxicol.* 18, 395–402.
696 <https://doi.org/10.1002/tox.10141>

697 RMC Remacon, n.d. Natural and synthetic graphite.

698 Rosales, S., Medina, O.E., Garzon, N., Zapata, K., Taborda, E.A., Ordóñez, J.C., Cortés,
699 F.B., Franco, C.A., 2025. Systematic review of carbon quantum dots (CQD):
700 Definition, synthesis, applications and perspectives. *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.*
701 219, 115854. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2025.115854>

702 Sanchís, J., Olmos, M., Vincent, P., Farré, M., Barceló, D., 2016. New Insights on the
703 Influence of Organic Co-Contaminants on the Aquatic Toxicology of Carbon
704 Nanomaterials. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 50, 961–969.
705 <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.5b03966>

706 Shenderova, O.A., Shames, A.I., Nunn, N.A., Torelli, M.D., Vlasov, I., Zaitsev, A., 2019.
707 Review Article: Synthesis, properties, and applications of fluorescent diamond
708 particles. *J. Vac. Sci. Technol. B* 37, 030802. <https://doi.org/10.1116/1.5089898>

709 Singh, H., Budiarto, H.A., Singh, B., Kumar, K., Gupta, R., Bhowmik, A., Santhosh, A.J.,
710 2025. Graphene for next-generation technologies: Advances in properties,
711 applications, and industrial integration. *Results Eng.* 27, 106865.
712 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rineng.2025.106865>

713 Singh, R.P., Das, M., Thakare, V., Jain, S., 2012. Functionalization Density Dependent
714 Toxicity of Oxidized Multiwalled Carbon Nanotubes in a Murine Macrophage Cell
715 Line. *Chem. Res. Toxicol.* 25, 2127–2137. <https://doi.org/10.1021/tx300228d>

716 Singla, A., Sankar, K.M., Singh, Y., 2020. Ecotoxicology: Methods and Risks, in:
717 Kharissova, O.V., Martínez, L.M.T., Kharisov, B.I. (Eds.), *Handbook of*
718 *Nanomaterials and Nanocomposites for Energy and Environmental Applications.*
719 Springer International Publishing, Cham, pp. 1–19. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-11155-7_92-1

720

721 Sweeney, S., Hu, S., Ruenaroengsak, P., Chen, S., Gow, A., Schwander, S., Zhang, J.
722 (Jim), Chung, K.F., Ryan, M.P., Porter, A.E., Shaffer, M.S., Tetley, T.D., 2016.
723 Carboxylation of multiwalled carbon nanotubes reduces their toxicity in primary

724 human alveolar macrophages. *Environ. Sci. Nano* 3, 1340–1350.
725 <https://doi.org/10.1039/C6EN00055J>

726 Trompeta, A.-F.A., Preiss, I., Ben-Ami, F., Benayahu, Y., Charitidis, C.A., 2019. Toxicity
727 testing of MWCNTs to aquatic organisms. *RSC Adv.* 9, 36707–36716.
728 <https://doi.org/10.1039/C9RA06672A>

729 Velzeboer, I., Hendriks, A.J., Ragas, A.M.J., Van De Meent, D., 2008. Nanomaterials in the
730 environment aquatic ecotoxicity tests of some nanomaterials. *Environ. Toxicol.*
731 *Chem.* 27, 1942–1947. <https://doi.org/10.1897/07-509.1>

732 Vulpe, C.-B., Toplicean, I.-M., Agachi, B.-V., Datcu, A.-D., 2025. A Review on Uses of
733 *Lemna minor*, a Beneficial Plant for Sustainable Water Treatments, in Relation to
734 Bioeconomy Aspects. *Water* 17, 1400. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w17091400>

735 Walker, C.H., Greig-Smith, P.W., Crossland, N.O., Brown, R., 1991. *Ecotoxicology* 223–
736 251. https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-349-12667-5_9

737 Walker, C.H., Hopkin, S.P., Sibly, R.M., Peakall, D.B., 2002. *Basics of ecotoxicology.*
738 PWN, Warsaw.

739 Wang, Y., Anilkumar, P., Cao, L., Liu, J.-H., Luo, P.G., Tackett, K.N., Sahu, S., Wang, P.,
740 Wang, X., Sun, Y.-P., 2011. Carbon dots of different composition and surface
741 functionalization: cytotoxicity issues relevant to fluorescence cell imaging. *Exp.*
742 *Biol. Med.* 236, 1231–1238. <https://doi.org/10.1258/ebm.2011.011132>

743 Xia, Z., Wen, Y., Jian, M., 2025. Introduction to carbon nanomaterials for smart
744 applications. *Nanoscale Adv.* 7, 1487–1488.
745 <https://doi.org/10.1039/D5NA90013A>

746 Yadav, R., Sharma, A.K., Sharma, S., 2025. Advance Development in Natural Graphite
747 Material and Its Applications: A Review. *Min. Metall. Explor.* 42, 361–385.
748 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42461-024-01167-z>

749 Yao, K., Lv, X., Zheng, G., Chen, Z., Jiang, Y., Zhu, X., Wang, Z., Cai, Z., 2018. Effects of
750 Carbon Quantum Dots on Aquatic Environments: Comparison of Toxicity to
751 Organisms at Different Trophic Levels. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 52, 14445–14451.
752 <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.8b04235>

753 Zhang, B., Feng, X., Yin, H., Ge, Z., Wang, Yanhuan, Chu, Z., Raabova, H., Vavra, J., Cigler,
754 P., Liu, R., Wang, Yi, Li, Q., 2017. Anchored but not internalized: shape dependent
755 endocytosis of nanodiamond. *Sci. Rep.* 7, 46462.
756 <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep46462>

757 Zhu, X., Zhu, L., Chen, Y., Tian, S., 2009. Acute toxicities of six manufactured
758 nanomaterial suspensions to *Daphnia magna*. *J. Nanoparticle Res.* 11, 67–75.
759 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11051-008-9426-8>